

RFC: File Locking Control in HDF5 1.10.x

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Version 1.10 of the HDF5 library uses a file locking scheme to help prevent reader/writer access patterns that can cause library errors, particularly with respect to the single-writer/multiple-readers (SWMR) access pattern. Although this scheme works well for many users, it has come to our attention that it can cause problems for others. Additional control over the file locking scheme would mitigate the issues that have been described to us.

This RFC provides an overview of the locking scheme, describes the problems that users have been encountering, and proposes some solutions. The implementation of the solutions are targeted for HDF5 1.10.1 (target release date: December 2016).

1 The HDF5 1.10.0 File Locking Scheme

1.1 File Exclusion Mechanisms

The HDF5 library employs two means to regulate access to HDF5 files under SWMR:

- a. File locking API calls to apply or remove an advisory lock on an open file. Note that these will also be used for non-SWMR access as a way to prevent inappropriate file access (e.g., two writers).
 - Files will be locked during the H5Fopen() or H5Fcreate() call.
 - Locks can be shared (read) or exclusive (write).
 - Locks will lock the entire file, not regions in the file.
 - When non-blocking lock calls are available, locks will not block.
 - Locks will be released automatically when the file closes. Alternatively, the user can unlock the file using the system's unlock call, however care will have to be taken to match the HDF5 library's file locking scheme.
- b. Setting a flag in the file's superblock to mark the file as open for writing.
 - The library will mark the file when opened for writing based on file open access flags. This will happen for both SWMR and non-SWMR reading. This marking ensures file consistency for concurrent accesses.
 - The library will clear the flag when the file closes.

1.2 Writer Actions

- When a writer process creates/opens a file without SWMR:

- Place an exclusive lock on the file—the file will remain locked until it closes.
- Ensure the file's superblock is not already marked for writing or SWMR writing mode.
- Mark the file's superblock for writing mode.
- When a writer process creates/opens a file with SWMR write access:
 - Place an exclusive lock on the file.
 - Ensure the file's superblock is not already marked for writing or SWMR writing mode.
 - Mark the file for writing and SWMR writing mode.
 - Release the lock before returning from *H5Fopen/H5Fcreate*.

Once a writer successfully opens/creates a file, no other writer can open/create the file (with or without SWMR). Readers cannot access the file either aside from one exception: if a writer has successfully opened the file with SWMR write, then a reader can access the file with SWMR read.

1.3 Reader Actions

- When a reader process opens a file without SWMR:
 - Place a shared lock on the file.
 - Ensure the file is not already marked for writing or SWMR writing mode.
- When a reader process opens a file with SWMR read:
 - Place a shared lock on the file.
 - Ensure the file is marked in writing and SWMR writing mode

Once a reader successfully opens a file, no writer can open the file (with or without SWMR); but other readers can access the file (with or without SWMR).

1.4 HDF5 Library Compatibility

HDF5 1.10.x	Full SWMR, respects locks and superblock
HDF5 1.8.y (y = TBD)	Will respect locks but not participate in SWMR
HDF5 1.8.0 - 1.8.(y-1)	Will ignore SWMR. All file open/create succeed.

1.5 SWMR Compatibility Matrices

The table below depicts the result of a second file open after the first open succeeds—file opens by writer and reader with combinations of access flags:

1st - 1.10 / 2nd 1.10

first open/create (1.10)

<i>file open access flags</i>	<i>read</i>	<i>write</i>	<i>SWMR read</i>	<i>SWMR write</i>
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Second open (1.10)	<i>read</i>	succeed	fail	succeed	fail
	<i>write</i>	fail	fail	fail	fail
	<i>SWMR read</i>	succeed	fail	succeed	succeed
	<i>SWMR write</i>	fail	fail	fail	fail

1st - 1.10 / 2nd 1.8.y+

first open/create (1.10)

second open (1.8.y+)	<i>file open access flags</i>	<i>read</i>	<i>write</i>	<i>SWMR read</i>	<i>SWMR write</i>
	<i>read</i>	succeed	fail	succeed	fail
	<i>write</i>	fail	fail	fail	fail
	<i>SWMR read</i>	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
	<i>SWMR write</i>	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

1st - 1.8.y+ / 2nd 1.10

first open/create (1.8.y+)

second open (1.10)	<i>file open access flags</i>	<i>read</i>	<i>write</i>	<i>SWMR read</i>	<i>SWMR write</i>
	<i>read</i>	succeed	fail	N/A	N/A
	<i>write</i>	fail	fail	N/A	N/A
	<i>SWMR read</i>	succeed	fail	N/A	N/A
	<i>SWMR write</i>	fail	fail	N/A	N/A

1st - 1.8.y+ / 2nd 1.8.y+

first open/create (1.8.y+)

second open (1.8.y+)	<i>file open access flags</i>	<i>read</i>	<i>write</i>	<i>SWMR read</i>	<i>SWMR write</i>
	<i>read</i>	succeed	fail	N/A	N/A
	<i>write</i>	fail	fail	N/A	N/A
	<i>SWMR read</i>	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
	<i>SWMR write</i>	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

2 Common File Locking Mechanisms

2.1 flock(2) ("BSD Locks")

In brief:

- Specified in 4.4BSD, though widely available. Occasionally implemented using the same primitives as `fcntl(2)`, *which implies those semantics - see below!* (NOTE: Linux does not do this).
- Allows getting, setting, and testing for the existence of both shared (read) and exclusive (write) locks.
- Locks are advisory.
- Locks are per-file. They cannot cover a particular region in the file.
- Any number of processes can hold a shared lock. Only one process can hold an exclusive lock. A single process cannot hold both a shared and exclusive lock for a file.
- Locks can be set to block or return immediately on failure to acquire.
- Locks are bound to a process and an open file table entry. File descriptors are considered independent and handled independently (i.e., a process with two file descriptors to the same file can block its own locks). File descriptors created via `dup()` or `fork()` are considered identical and will be closed when all duplicated descriptors are closed or an unlock operation takes place on any descriptor.
- Any lock can be placed on a file regardless of how it was opened (read/write).
- Locks are preserved across `fork()` and `execve()`.
- NOTE: BSD and POSIX locks do not necessarily interact. i.e., a BSD lock is not guaranteed to be respected by a call to `fcntl(2)`.

2.2 fcntl(2) ("POSIX Locks")

In brief:

- Specified in SVr4, 4.3 BSD, and POSIX.1-2001 (very widely available).
- Allows getting, setting, and testing for the existence of both shared (read) and exclusive (write) locks.
- Locks are advisory.
- Locks can cover regions of the file at byte-level granularity. The entire file can also be locked.
- Any number of processes can hold a shared lock. Only one process can hold an exclusive lock. Only one type of lock can be held for a region, though a process may hold both shared and exclusive region locks throughout a file.
- Locks can be set to block or return immediately on failure to acquire.

- Exclusive locks require a file being opened in write or read-write mode, shared locks require a file being opened in read or read-write mode.
- Locks are bound to a process and an inode (*not* a file descriptor). This means that a process closing any file descriptor for the file will release all fcntl locks. This can be a problem if another part of the code opens and closes a file for any reason, say, as an existence test.
- Locks are not preserved across fork() but are preserved across execve().
- POSIX locks have trouble with stdio buffering and will be disabled in the stdio VFD.
- Mandatory locks are non-POSIX. The Linux implementation is known to have severe race conditions. All mandatory locking has corner cases that allow bypassing the lock (e.g., unlink() often ignores mandatory locks). File systems must often be specially mounted to take advantage of them.
- Note: our implementation ignores fcntl64(2) on Linux, since this is handled transparently.
- lockf(3) is usually implemented using the same primitives as fcntl(2) locking.
- NOTE: BSD and POSIX locks do not necessarily interact. i.e., a BSD lock is not guaranteed to be respected by a call to fcntl(2).

2.3 lockf(3)

lockf(3) is almost always implemented using the same mechanism as fcntl(2)¹ so we will not specifically address it here.

2.4 Win32

We currently do not support any file locking mechanism on Windows, though this is planned for a later release of HDF5 1.10. In the meantime, it is up to the user to prevent inappropriate HDF5 file access.

3 Problems

3.1 Locks Present At Configure But Unimplemented or Disabled on File System

We've had many reports where file locking is present at configure time and/or on the build file system, but is unimplemented or disabled on the file system where the I/O takes place. This is the most commonly reported file locking problem and is the highest priority to fix. Any solution should assume that the configure step cannot determine if file locking is present and functional.

3.2 flock(2) Lock Contention

We've received a report that holding a large number of shared locks open can cause a shared lock operation to fail.

¹ No system where this is not true has been identified.

3.3 Some Users May Prefer `fcntl(2)` Locks

`flock(2)` and `fcntl(2)` are often implemented using different underlying mechanisms and have different semantics. HDF5 1.10.0 defaults to using `flock(2)`, but users may prefer `fcntl(2)`, either for the different semantics or to interact with an existing file locking scheme based on `fcntl(2)`.

To date, this has not been requested and is therefore lower priority.

4 Proposed Solutions

4.1 Check `errno` After A Failed Lock Call

One very easy thing we can do is check `errno` for the `ENOSYS` "unimplemented" value after the lock call and have the HDF5 API call succeed anyway when it's set². This could either be the default behavior or it could be enabled by the user via a configure option, API call, or environment variable.

Another option that should almost certainly be implemented, is that the HDF5 library could check the `errno` value and emit a more helpful error message when it appears that file locking is unimplemented on the file system.

Advantages

- Easy to implement
- Users do not have to do anything to get the benefit
- Portable

Disadvantages

- Has semantic issues: Users will be less protected from bad behavior than they believe if we ignore "unimplemented" flock errors.

4.2 `H5Pset/get_use_file_locking()` and `H5Pset/get_file_locking_scheme()`

Another option would be to offer an API call that would enable users to selectively enable or disable file locking. This could either take a Boolean parameter that switches the default file locking scheme on and off or it could take an enumeration parameter that selects from various file locking systems (including "none").

```
H5Pset_use_file_locking(hid_t fapl, hbool_t use_locking)
```

or

```
H5Pset_file_locking_scheme(hid_t fapl, H5F_lock_scheme_t scheme)
```

Advantages

² According to POSIX.1c, `errno` MUST be thread-safe.

- Straightforward to implement
- Portable if it just takes a Boolean switch.

Disadvantages

- Applications will require code changes in order to function. Binaries and complicated software will not be easy to modify.
- Has portability problems with the enum type if one or more of the file locking schemes were not present on the system. We would probably also want to implement an API call that returns a list of valid file locking schemes, but even then that would probably be determined by configure-level checks and would not be a list of useful locking schemes on a given file system.

4.3 --enable/disable-file-locking Configure Option

This would enable (or disable) file locking for the entire library. If `H5Pset_file_locking_scheme()` were implemented, we would have to decide how the two features would interact. The `H5Pset` call could either fail or, alternatively, be allowed to override the configure option.

Advantages

- Straightforward to implement
- Portable
- Once the library is built, no other code changes are necessary.

Disadvantages

- Needs to be maintained in both the Autotools and CMake.
- Interaction with `H5Pset_file_locking_scheme()` could be confusing for users.
- Without an `H5P_set_file_locking_scheme()` override, there is no way to use the file locking scheme when disabled at configure time.

4.4 --with-locking-scheme=(flock|fcntl) Configure Option

This would allow selecting flock vs fcntl (and possibly even lockf(3), for completeness) as the default locking scheme at the library level. If we add "none" to this option, we would also get the same behavior as --enable/disable-file-locking (above).

Advantages

- Straightforward to implement
- Once the library is built, no other code changes are necessary.

Disadvantages

- Needs to be maintained in both the Autotools and CMake.

- Interaction with `H5Pset_file_locking_scheme()` could be confusing for users.
- Without an `H5P_set_file_locking_scheme()` override that takes an enum type, there is no way to override the file locking scheme when set at configure time.

4.5 Control File Locking Via An Environment Variable

Another option is to control the file locking via an environment variable (e.g. `HDF5_ENABLE_SWMR_FILE_LOCKS`). Valid values would be `TRUE` and `FALSE`. Alternatively, this could be named `HDF5_SWMR_FILE_LOCK_SCHEME` and extended to take `(flock|fcntl|none)`.

Advantages

- Easy to implement
- An on/off flag would be portable.
- Existing code does not have to be re-written.

Disadvantages

- Taking `flock|fcntl|none` would take more time to implement and might have portability issues if certain locking schemes are not present on the system.

4.6 Remove File Locking Entirely

A final option is to remove the file locking scheme entirely. This would place the burden of enforcing SWMR semantics entirely on users.

Advantages

- Easy to implement
- Portable
- Returns library behavior to HDF5 1.8.x default, which is well-understood by users.

Disadvantages

- Changes library semantics between HDF5 1.10.0 and 1.10.1.
- Makes using SWMR (actually, any HDF5 file access) more error-prone.
- Does not protect users from other dangerous file access patterns (e.g.: multiple writers).

5 Testing

Testing the feature will be difficult since it will be difficult to duplicate the failure conditions. We can't set up a file system with disabled locking in the tests and it would be difficult to purposely cause shared lock contention.

File locking is currently tested in the test/swmr.c file. Several tests in this will have to be modified to either pass when file locking is disabled or to also investigate the behavior of any new H5P API calls.

Configure options would either be tested manually or various values could be exercised via the daily tests.

6 Recommendations

As a primary solution, I would recommend implementing the environment variable solution described in section 4.5. The environment variable will just take TRUE/FALSE. This will allow users to control the file locking without having to rebuild the library or change existing code.

I would also recommend that we check the errno value when acquiring a lock fails so we can emit a better error message when file locking is unimplemented or disabled.

Other options could be implemented in the future, if the environment variable proves insufficient.

Acknowledgements

This work is being internally funded by The HDF Group.

Revision History

- June 2, 2016:* Version 1 (outline only) circulated for comment within The HDF Group.
- October 12, 2016:* Version 2 circulated for comment within The HDF Group.
- October 16, 2016:* Version 3 circulated for comment on the forum.

References

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